

Response to Mao D et al. AI-MARRVEL — A Knowledge-Driven AI System for Diagnosing Mendelian Disorders. NEJM-AI 2024;1(5).

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We were surprised by the low reported performances for the external tools in Figure 1 of Mao et al ¹, e.g., the top ranked recall of the diagnoses for 200 Deciphering Developmental Disorder (DDD) cases of ~15%, ~16%, and ~30% for Exomiser 13.1.0, PhenIX 1.16 and LIRICAL 1.3.4 respectively, compared to ~65% for their software. Earlier this year an independent group published benchmarking of the same versions of Exomiser, PhenIX and LIRICAL on a superset of the same DDD cohort and showed top ranked performances of 62%, 50% and 47% respectively². As shown below, we also find very similar performances and little or no improvement from using AI-MARRVEL on the DDD cohort or on a further set of 4529 samples. Evaluating variant prioritization software is challenging due to the lack of openly available rare disease cohorts and the complexity of installing and correctly configuring the tools, e.g. see previous discussion of these issues^{3,4}. Therefore we have developed the PhEval framework (<https://github.com/monarch-initiative/pheval>)⁵ that provides standardization of evaluation cohorts, software runners and benchmarking statistics and visualization. A cohort of 4529 curated Phenopackets⁶ and VCFs from published case reports is provided as part of the framework, as well as the ability to run evaluations on simulated samples or real clinical data such as DDD or in-house cohorts.

We were able to run PhEval on the full superset of 359 diagnosed DDD cases and our case reports for AI-MARRVEL and the same version of Exomiser they evaluated. Unfortunately, AI-MARRVEL was unable to run 51 of the DDD singleton samples as, unlike Exomiser, it was not able to convert the original DDD HPO IDs to the most recent IDs. To allow a fair comparison we excluded these samples and assessed the remaining 308. Further problems with AI-MARRVEL were experienced when running the DDD trio samples so here we had to restrict the comparison to 260 samples. As shown below, the performance for all tools was similar with AI-MARRVEL having slightly higher top-ranked accuracy for DDD singletons but Exomiser performing better for the DDDs trio and 4529 case reports. This contradicts their findings and suggests they are either using suboptimal, non-default settings for the external software (unfortunately exact parameters are not described in the paper) and/or a biased subset of the DDD cases in their selection of 200 samples (again no data is provided on why these 200 were chosen out of the full DDD cohort). In conclusion, we urge the community to present benchmarking results on standardized cohorts and with transparent settings for each tool to allow accurate and efficient comparisons and propose PhEval as a solution for this.

1. Mao, Dongxue, Chaozhong Liu, Linhua Wang, Rami Ai-Ouran, Cole Deisseroth, Sasidhar Pasupuleti, Seon Young Kim, et al. 2024. "AI-MARRVEL - A Knowledge-Driven AI System for Diagnosing Mendelian Disorders." *NEJM AI* 1 (5).
2. Yuan, X. *et al.* Refined preferences of prioritizers improve intelligent diagnosis for Mendelian diseases. *Sci. Rep.* **14**, 2845 (2024).
3. Jacobsen, J. O. B., Kelly, C., Cipriani, V., Robinson, P. N. & Smedley, D. Evaluation of phenotype-driven gene prioritization methods for Mendelian diseases. *Brief. Bioinform.* **23**, (2022).
4. Yuan, X. & Zhang, P. Revisiting benchmark study for response to methodological critiques of 'Evaluation of phenotype-driven gene prioritization methods for Mendelian diseases'. *Brief. Bioinform.* **23**, (2022).
5. Bridges, Y. *et al.* Towards a standard benchmark for variant and gene prioritisation algorithms: PhEval - Phenotypic inference Evaluation framework. *bioRxiv* (2024)
6. Danis, Daniel, Michael J. Bamshad, Yasemin Bridges, Pilar Cacheiro, Leigh C. Carmody, Jessica X. Chong, Ben Coleman, et al. 2024. "A Corpus of GA4GH Phenopackets: Case-Level Phenotyping for Genomic Diagnostics and Discovery." *MedRxiv: The Preprint Server for Health Sciences*, May. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.05.29.24308104>